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EMOTIONAL INVESTMENT IN MILITARY FORCES: A FORCE MULTIPLIER IN ORGANIZATIONAL DEVELOPMENT AND SECURITY

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Abstract

Humans are more emotional than rational beings. Emotions win over logic often always while making any decision both on a personal and collective level. The sense of belongingness, attachment, nationalistic feelings, love for the organization, and a sense of patriotism are the consequences of emotional investments. Emotions are precious human assets; therefore, emotions must be constructively cultivated for growth and security in any institution. This study focuses on revitalizing the emotional investment for any organizational success, especially in the military. Leaders and commanders will find a more plausible logic for emotional safety needs to endure the success of their organizations through this epistle.

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Introduction

1.1 An isolated human on a remote island may not survive for long since humans are group living creatures and not self-sufficient in most cases. People need others' help to catch fish and hunt for meat; they need the assistance of others to build a shelter. We need protection while at rest or to safeguard property. Who is better suited to match the survival necessity in a distant jungle between a human and a monkey? The monkey is a better suit than that a human. However, who may live better with superior survival rates if 1000 monkeys and 1000 humans are in the same jungle? In such cases, humans will not only survive better but also build and accomplish the impossible through cooperation, coordination, and sharing; however, the monkeys will remain as they have lived in the jungle for thousands of years. When people are living in a group, they can achieve much greater things than single living. Living in a group is vital for humans, but what is the core source of building group identity? What special quality do humans possess that keeps people in utmost unity? This study may answer such questions as many researchers

have tried to address this issue. To pursue organizational development, stability, and security, this study will assist all responsible for organizing and leading a group of people, especially military and business leaders.

1.2 Humans are predominantly emotional beings. Unseen, untouchable, with no taste or smell, emotional feelings are the most valued features of our daily life. Every one of us seeks care, respect, and love. We want love from our family, friends, relatives, and neighbors. We enjoy being loved and feel an urgency to love our children, parents, friends, and others who love us. The necessity of love and respect makes us so much moved that our entire life becomes a pursuit of these superlative feelings. Love makes our life so colorful that the absence of this feeling causes a lot of emotional, psychological, and even physical imbalances. We cannot imagine our life without love and attachment. A sense of respect fulfills our life; honor makes sense of fulfillment, and pride gives us inner force. Such needs compel us to live in a group since we enjoy sharing our feelings and opt for respect, dignity, admiration, and affection.

1.3 Greek philosopher Aristotle said emotions are an essential component of virtue that enhances human capacities. Current research also suggests that emotion is vital to human behavior, decision-making, and planning. Emotion works as an adhesive to cause human bonding with each other. Individual bonding is critical for small spheres like family or friends, but group bonding is vital to organizational or social strength. Group bonding members was one of the necessities in prehistoric hunters' life for teamwork, mutual aid, and group actions to bring down large animals and obtain meat for their clans. With the advent of the city-state, its social and community system, organized warfare, bonding, attachment, and cohesion became important as a strategic technology for overcoming challenges and realizing organizational growth.

1.4 In an organizational environment, every leader wants to be loved by their men. Attachment is vital between leaders and followers; bonding is also critical among members and organs of any system. People seek attachments with leaders and peers (Bales, 1950) as belongingness enhances support, general well-being, health (Cohen & Wills, 1985), and performance. Therefore,

interpersonal and group bonding is often synonymous with productivity and security. In achieving organizational success, leaders must address the dynamic social environment by managing their feelings about themselves and the people they lead. More precisely, leadership's effectiveness depends on leaders' ability to tie their people's emotions with the purpose of work, peers, leadership environment, and ways in life.

1.5 Interpersonal bonding among service personnel paves the military unity and group effort. It enhances performance and confidence through dependency and trust. Increasing evidence in recent years seems to suggest that the emotional bonding of military units needs to be carefully studied and measures to be taken to enhance the performance effectiveness of its members. Considering the importance and its effect, very recently, emotional intelligence has emerged as one of the unique behavior effectiveness concepts. It is claimed to be a foundational element of leadership effectiveness now. Building emotional attachment is one of the primary necessities of leadership attributes, especially for transformational leadership in many organizations worldwide. Despite evidence suggesting that group attachment has positive mental health outcomes among service members, it has yet to be formally examined for performance effectiveness in many Armed Forces. Such knowledge could assist commanders and policymakers as a critical facet of military education and the comprehensive attitude development process. Many organizations are yet to formally focus on people's bonding with the institution as a vital necessity, although an informal approach is often found embedded. Colonial military inheritance in many Armed Forces often does not prioritize the research and development on human bonding and yet to accept it through cultural integration in their institution.

Significance of the Study

2.1 Maximizing performance effectiveness is one of the most critical issues often discussed because it affects not only the well-being but also the existence of an individual, group, unit, or even organization. Performance effectiveness is the outcome of an organizational system through its members' sincere commitment and dedication. A growing organization moves by ensuring the

essential needs of the members and providing a fear-free working environment. A constructive social environment, fairness while dealing, mutual respect, and emotional investments are critical in spontaneous motivation among men. Without emotional bonding with the leadership environment, people often may pass through discontentment, and performance may suffer a setback.

2.2 There are numerous examples in military history where a strongly bonded yet small combat team outperformed a loosely bonded superior force. As such, comradeship becomes the most valuable in unit performance, and military commanders take every opportunity to foster bonding among their men. There are also examples in many societies where people have saved the lives and properties of opponent groups only because of interpersonal bonding among them. Indeed, emotional bonding is a security shield in a family, group, unit organization, society, or nation. It comes through love, care, and fairness in the working environment. When people engage in hostility, they cause damage and kill each other's lives and property. Nevertheless, there are also instances of putting own people in danger due to poor bonding among the team members. Love and care for others can turn impossible in society. The same is also observed in other creatures. Lions are fetal and destructive animals, but when loved, cared for, and well-trained, they become emotionally attached to humans. Thus emotional investment among people, leaders, and the institution work as one of the powerful multipliers to shape organizational climate, which can eventually maximize any organization's or society's performance effectiveness.

2.3 Threats and insecurity in any institution are often inevitable phenomena that may arise in many forms, ranging from deliberate violation of instruction by the people to accidental circumstances. It may also come from an adverse social sensation or a byproduct of organizational changes or mistakes. As nature is rolling through the cause-and-effect phenomenon, performance effectiveness is also the logical outcome of definite causes and effects. Every performance inability has undeniable root causes, and every aspect of success also has certain governing psychological factors. In the ever-changing social environment of the Information Age, emotional bonding among leaders and followers is a critical issue to enhance and maximize operational effectiveness through emotional bonding between people and the institution.

2.4 There are a lot of studies available on the causes, effects, and exploration of solutions to maximize performance effectiveness in organizations; however, care-based emotional bonding is yet to be recognized as a priority in many institutions to enhance human performance. It may be necessary to address this issue in depth and find means to invest more in emotional bonding and cohesion through cultural integration in organizations.

Exploration of Literature

Meaning and Measurement of Bonding and Cohesion

3.1 Cohesion and attachment are synonymous with group bonding which has been studied and is widely used as a variable in numerous pieces of research. Nonetheless, it remained problematic as a concept and in its measurement for a long past. In 1985, Drescher, Burlingame, and Fuhrman stated, "Attempts to understand cohesion empirically have been as elusive as attempts to define it." Levine and Moreland (1990) reported that, in comprehending organizational cohesion, the main issue is "how the cohesion of a group should be conceptualized and measured where there is much confusion regarding that issue." Drescher et al., Guzzo, and Dickson (1996) noted that "the topic of cohesiveness is still very much an unsettled concern in the literature." The reasons for the troubles with the concept of cohesion and its measurement items are too vast. Most researchers revolved around the term cohesion or group bonding, a concept that is easy to understand in the abstract but complex and challenging to grasp.

Group bonding or cohesion is a concept of widely associated terms that may be easy to understand as an abstract but complex to formulate a single policy to achieve it.

3.2 Group bonding is positively related to a caring attitude felt among employees (Burt et al., 2008; Geller, Roberts, & Gilmore, 1996; Roberts & Geller, 1995). People who feel caring attitudes to the organizational climate enhance organizational success. These people spontaneously cooperate at work by helping and warning others about safety issues and recognizing coworkers' limits (Burt et al., 2008). Group attachment and bonding are vital for industrial, organizational, and sports psychologists (Dion, 2000). According to Luria (2008), unity generates through social bonding among peers who share everyday tasks and collective activities. Social bonding develops cohesion among people and is related to job performance, job satisfaction, general well-being, and effectiveness. Several previous studies have shown that group bonding has a normative function in the shaping of individual behavior (e.g., Andriessen, 1978; Simard & Marchand, 1997) and strongly influences individual attitudes.

Both team and individual bonding are essential for organizational development. Group bonding shapes individual behavior and attitude. Group attachment deals with psychological distress, stress management, depression, loneliness, social anxiety, and the development of normative functions for general well-being. Thus bonding among people largely influences productivity and safety in any institution.

Emotional Investment Enhances Security and Cooperation

3.3 Along with the growth, the security of an institution is a vital point of concern in any organization. Insecurity may arise from any corner; however, humans working inside the team are often considered the weakest link in the chain of effective security management and control (Crossler et al., 2013; Ifinedo, 2014). At times, the insider is viewed as a serious threat to organizations' resources, information, and safety (Boss et al., 2009; Symantec Corporation, 2014; PricewaterhouseCoopers, 2015). A trade report in the business industry indicated that executives believe the actions of a company's employees pose more immediate danger than external threats (CITI, 2015). The report shows that employees commit more than 50 percent of security breaches in their organizations (PricewaterhouseCoopers, 2015). In brief, insider behavior often facilitates breaches of an organization's assets (Lowry & Moody, 2015).

Members who strongly bond with peers and organizational visions are more positive about safety and security instruction.

3.4 Cooperation and collaboration within organizations are vital to establishing a secure working environment. Researchers (Cheng et al., 2013; Ifinedo, 2014; Safa et al., 2016) have used Social Bond Theory proposed by Hirschi(1969) to investigate security instructions compliance. These studies demonstrated that members who strongly bonded with colleagues and their organizations were more likely to comply with security-related instructions. The theory postulates that when people build upon such attachment, their urge to indulge in antisocial or anti-establishment behaviors gets reduced. Hirschi presented four bonds by which socialization and social conformity can be promoted, i.e., attachment, commitment, involvement, and personal norms, that shape the organizational climate. It has been shown that when coworkers develop strong bonds with colleagues, such attachments collectively make them more agreeable to upholding organizational values(Steers, 1977; Robinson et al., 1998; Thomas & Griffin, 1989).

3.5 In the military, peer bonding is a necessity to deal with psychological distress, combat stress reactions, depression, loneliness, anxiety, and battlefield field trauma (e.g., Ahronson& Cameron, 2007; Griffith, 2002; Manning, 1991; Oliver, Harman, Hoover, Hayes, &Pandhi, 1999; Wech et al., 1998), both at individual and group levels (Gully, Devine, & Whitney, 1995). Individual attachment to the group reflects individual team members' feelings about personal involvement; however, group integration reflects individual team members' perceptions about closeness and bonding regarding the team's social activities. Oliver et al.'s (1999) meta-analysis of the military literature says attachment, bonding, and cohesion are more strongly related to soldier perceptions of satisfaction with the military way of life than to any other outcome. Theoretical arguments for cohesion and attachment to the organizational working environment (Hogg, 1992; Hogg &Hains, 1996) have also included individual identification with the group. Among all the variables examined, Shamir, Brainin, Zakay, and Popper (2000) observed that soldier identification with the unit had the most substantial positive relation to combat readiness. Time and duration impact a lot. The longer the experience of unit soldiers in the army, the higher the perceived combat readiness of the unit. In their study of German Wehrmacht soldiers in

World War II, Shils and Janowitz (1948) found that high levels of cohesion characterized German Army units that resisted disintegration despite overwhelming odds.

3.6 Responding to the need to increase service members' attachment to organizations, the US military invested in many family services to families and individual soldiers. With the motto "Stronger Relationships Mean a Stronger Army." They also undertook the Army Strong Bonds Program, which offered a range of relationship education and skills training programs (www.strongbonds.org) typically led by unit chaplains. Following this program, the USA continues to provide relationship training tools for soldiers and their families. Each year commanders from the Active and reserve Army, National Guard, and other forces plan more than 5000 strong bonds events with the conclusion of healthy relationships contributing to maintaining a healthy and secure future force. Research shows that training in communication skill, intimacy, conflict, and expectation management increases marital satisfaction and reduce rates of family violence.

3.7 In the military, peacetime or wartime support is best captured through mutual bonding among units, military culture, norms, and practices built by a strong sense of cohesion and morale (Britt, Adler, Bliese, & Moore, 2013; Griffith, 1989). Service members' relationships with unit leadership and peers are core dimensions of such attachment (Griffith, 2002; Manning, 1991). Bonding often reflects a group's propensity to work as a collective team while pursuing objectives (Carron & Brawley, 2000; Carron, Brawley, & Widmeyer, 1998). It is also observed that higher levels of cohesion are associated with decreased levels of psychological distress among people (Brailey, Vasterling, Proctor, Constans, & Friedman, 2007; Halverson, Bliese, Moore, & Castro, 1995; Mulligan et al., 2010). Strong unit bonding in the military is also associated with greater well-being, work performance, combat readiness, job satisfaction, and increased retention levels (Cota, Evans, Dion, Kilik, & Longman, 1995; Griffith, 2002; Halverson et al., 1995; Mullen & Copper, 1994; Oliver, Harman, Hoover, Hayes, & Pandhi, 1999). Military members have shared experiences that help unit-level mutual and emotional exchange support that may help deal with stress. Calhoun and Tedeschi (2004) found that those individuals who lived through similar traumatic experiences possess superior shave more

credibility, and their support can help others within the group confront and incorporate new perspectives.

A service member's relationships with unit leadership and peers are core dimensions of unit cohesion, performance, combat readiness, and credibility through shared experiences.

Ways to Foster Group Bonding

3.8 The question of what causes strong organizational bonding to grow or diminish is important more on practical grounds. Theoretically, such knowledge is necessary to specify better; however, in practical terms, a better grasp of the factors that lead to increased bonding will facilitate structuring organizational policies and training programs to build and maintain bonding in work groups quickly. It is an especially important issue for the military because modern operations rely more heavily on rapidly organized task forces tailored for particular missions than in the past.

3.9 Expanding on this theme, Lott and Lott (1965) suggested that cohesion grows when there is shared responsibility among group members concerning some external threat. Along similar lines, Gal (1983), Manning (1991), and Marlowe (1985) all argued that the shared experience of stressful events serves to build interpersonal bonding among soldiers in military units. Siebold (1987) identified that proximity of group members over time, social similarities or commonalities, and success at common tasks influence group cohesion: Lott and Lott also posited that homogeneity of status and background similarities contribute to group cohesion. Hogg listed the following factors that can influence cohesion among people: inter-action or propinquity, a cooperative versus competitive group atmosphere, small group size, acceptance by others, frustration or threat (stress), status similarity or dissimilarity, personality characteristics of group members, similarity in the background and social characteristics, successful performance and reward, and unpleasant initiation rites.

3.10 Concerning military groups, good leadership is a critical factor influencing group cohesion, but the core capacity lies with the organizational culture. Several authors have suggested that leaders whom soldiers perceive as caring and competent can positively influence the development of cohesion (Griffith, 1985; Ingraham & Manning, 1981; Kirkland, 1987; Kirkland, Bartone, & Marlowe, 1993; Manning, 1991; Marlowe, 1985; Siebold & Kelly, 1988). Researchers found that "small units that have been together as units for a long time have higher unit bonding levels than recently formed units. Bonding includes horizontal cohesion (soldier to soldier) and vertical cohesion between the upper and lower tier.

Group bonding is influenced by the proximity of group members, social similarities, and success or failure at joining tasks. Small group size, status resemblance, organizational culture, and living long in a particular group enhance unity.

Culture is a Powerful Tool

3.11 Aristotle believed that emotions were an essential component of virtue and that all emotions corresponded to appetites or capacities. Contemporary views along the evolutionary spectrum posit that basic and social emotions evolved to motivate adaptive human behaviors in the ancestral environment. Current research suggests that emotion is essential to any human decision-making and planning. Canadian philosopher Paul Thagard, Ph.D. described four kinds of power in interpersonal relations that rely on emotional effects; among them, culture seems to be the most powerful. He says social norms and habits make people comply with a plan through agreements that seem to them voluntary. Such voluntary compliance can drive and control people while believing they are making their own choices for the role assigned. People feel proud and self-satisfied with following their mental habits, whereas violations of norms lead to negative emotions such as shame, guilt, and self-loathing. At full emotional complexity, social roles can operate as fear of embarrassment and pride of obedience. Thus people absorb some values as central to an ideology.

Emotions are essential human virtue, motivating force, and part of the decision-making process. Social or group norms in the form of culture can develop positive emotions in which people feel proud and self-satisfied. In contrast, violations can lead to negative emotions.